

Successive ratio spectra derivative method for simultaneous determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol in some pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : Successive ratio derivative method based on the spectrophotometric data has been developed for the simultaneous determination of a ternary mixture containing aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol, without prior separation. The method is based on the successive derivative of ratio spectra in two steps. The mathematical explanation of the procedure is illustrated. The concentrations of three compounds in their mixture are determined by using their respective standard addition plots at either the maximum/minimum selected wavelengths. The selected wavelengths for determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol are 296.0, 257 and 261.0 nm respectively. The mean recoveries for determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol were 100.8, 99.4 and 100.0 respectively in some ternary mixtures with the limit of detections ($3S_b$) as 0.29, 0.76 and 0.48 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ in Britton-Robinson buffer solution (pH 11.0). The method was applied successfully for the analysis of Afebryl tablet and effervescent powders containing aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol.

Keywords : Aspirin, ascorbic acid, paracetamol, successive ratio derivative method, analysis.

Introduction

The main problem of spectrophotometric multicomponent analysis is the simultaneous determination of two or more compounds in the same mixtures without preliminary separation. Several spectrophotometric determination methods have been used for resolving mixtures of compounds with overlapping spectra such as partial least squares regression (PLSR)¹, principal component regression (PCR)², multi-wavelength linear regression analysis (MLRA)³ and H-point standard addition method (HPSAM) for binary and ternary mixtures have been utilized^{4,5}. When these methods are compared with each other, the range of application of derivative spectrophotometry is more reliable with respect to utility and sensitivity than normal spectrophotometry⁶⁻¹⁰.

Salinas¹¹ and Berzas Nevado *et al.*¹² developed two methods for the resolution of two or more compounds in mixtures by ratio spectra derivative spectrophotometry and the derivative ratio spectra-zero crossing method. Salinas' method is based on the use of the derivative of the ratio spectra for a binary mixture. The absorption spec-

trum of the mixture is divided by the absorption spectrum of one of the compounds and the first derivative of the ratio spectrum is obtained. The concentrations of active compounds are then determined from the calibration graphs obtained by measuring the amplitudes at points corresponding to the minimum or maximum wavelengths. In Berzas Nevado's method, the simultaneous determinations of three compounds in ternary mixtures are based on the measurements of the amplitude at the zero crossing points in the derivative spectrum of the ratio spectra.

Recently, Dinc *et al.*^{13,14} proposed a new spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous determination of ternary mixtures. This method was called "the double divisor ratio spectra derivative method". The method is based on the use of the coincident spectra of the derivative of the ratio spectra obtained by using a "double divisor" (sum of two spectra) and the measuring at either the maximum or minimum wavelengths. But their method can't be popularized, because it can only be used for the mixtures that the ratio of the concentrations of two interfering compounds (used as double divisor) is known. In

the other words, the ratio of the concentrations of two interfering compounds should be the same in calibration, prediction and unknown samples. It is obvious that the ratio of the concentration of the analytes in real samples is always unknown.

In this research, successive ratio derivative method has been applied for simultaneous determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol in ternary mixtures. This method is based on the successive derivative of ratio spectra in two successive steps as shown in the theoretical section. The proposed method has been successfully applied to the determination of ASP, AA and PAR in Afebryl tablet and effervescent powder.

Experimental

Reagents :

Aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol were kindly gifted by the Iranian Pharmaceutical Companies (Tehran, Iran). Analytical grade phosphoric acid, boric acid, acetic acid and sodium hydroxide were supplied from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). All other reagents were of analytical grade. Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer (0.1 mol L^{-1}) in the pH range of 2–10 was used throughout.

A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ aspirin solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0090 g aspirin (99.0%) in ethanol (96%) and was diluted in a 50 ml volumetric flask to the mark. A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ ascorbic acid solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0088 g of ascorbic acid (99.5%) in ethanol (96%) and diluted in a 50 ml volumetric flask. A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ paracetamol solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0074 g of paracetamol (99.5%) in double distilled water and diluted into a 50 ml volumetric flask. These solutions were kept in a refrigerator at 4 °C in dark. More dilute solutions were prepared by serial dilutions with double distilled water.

Instrumentation and software :

UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded by a spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer) model Lambda 25, with the use of 1.0 cm quartz cells.

A Pentium IV (2.53 GHz) computer controlled all the setting and data processing. The spectrum of each solution were recorded in the wavelength range of 200–320 nm and saved as text files. Successive ratio derivative spectra calculated in Excel (2007) program.

A pH-meter (Metrohm, Model 827) with a double junction glass electrode was used to adjust the pH of the solutions.

Preparation of real samples :

To assay Afebryl tablet containing aspirin (300 mg), ascorbic acid (300 mg) and paracetamol (200 mg) in each tablet, the content of five tablets were mixed completely. The quantity of 0.8 g of the powder was accurately weighted and then dissolved in 100 mL of ethanol (96%). After being solved completely, the solution was diluted to the mark with ethanol. This solution was kept in refrigerator at 4 °C.

For analysis of effervescent powder containing aspirin (66.0 mg) and ascorbic acid (3.7 mg) in each 100 mg of the powder, the quantity of 0.1 g of the powder was accurately weighted and then dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol (96%). After being solved completely, the solution was diluted to the mark with ethanol. This solution was kept in refrigerator at 4 °C.

General procedure :

The general procedure for the analysis of PAR, ASP and CAF in a ternary mixture was as follows. To approximately 1.0 ml of sample solution in a 10.0 ml volumetric flask, 1.0 ml B-R buffer (pH 4.0) was added and the final volume was diluted to the mark with double distilled water after successive standard additions of three components (ASP, AA and PAR) at the same mole ratio. For simultaneous determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol, the spectra of ternary mixture after each standard addition recorded in the wavelength range of 200–400 nm. Then, the spectra of the mixture divided to the spectrum of a standard solution containing one of the components. The ratio spectra were transformed to Excel software and converted to derivative ratio spectra. The values of ASP, AA and PAR in the ternary mixtures were determined by standard addition plots at wavelengths 296, 257 and 261 nm respectively recorded at the final successive ratio spectra derivative.

Theoretical background :

Consider a mixture of three compounds X, Y and Z. If Beer's law is obeyed for all compounds over the whole wavelength range used and by considering the path length of 1.0 cm, the absorbance of the ternary mixture at each wavelength can be written as :

$$A_m = \epsilon_X C_X + \epsilon_Y C_Y + \epsilon_Z C_Z \quad (1)$$

where A_m is the vector of the absorbance of the mixture,

ϵ_X , ϵ_Y and ϵ_Z are the absorptivity vectors of X, Y and Z and C_X , C_Y and C_Z are the concentrations of X, Y and Z, respectively.

If eq. (1) is divided by ϵ_Z corresponding to the spectrum of a standard solution of Z in ternary mixture, the first ratio spectrum is obtained in the form of eq. (2) (for possibility of dividing operation, the zero values of ϵ_Z should not be used in the divisor) :

$$B = \frac{A_m}{\epsilon_Z} = \frac{\epsilon_X C_X}{\epsilon_Z} + \frac{\epsilon_Y C_Y}{\epsilon_Z} + C_Z \quad (2)$$

If the first derivative of eq. (2) is taken, since the derivative of a constant (C_Z) is zero, eq. (3) would be obtained :

$$\frac{dB}{d\lambda} = \frac{d}{d\lambda} \left[\frac{\epsilon_X C_X}{\epsilon_Z} \right] + \frac{d}{d\lambda} \left[\frac{\epsilon_Y C_Y}{\epsilon_Z} \right] \quad (3)$$

By dividing eq. (3) by $(d/d\lambda)(\epsilon_Y/\epsilon_Z)$, corresponding to the derivative of the ratio of the spectra of the standard solutions of Y and Z, the second ratio spectrum is obtained as eq. (4) (for possibility of dividing operation, the zero values of $(d/d\lambda)(\epsilon_Y/\epsilon_Z)$ should not be used in the divisor) :

$$D = \frac{dB/d\lambda}{(d/d\lambda)(\epsilon_Y/\epsilon_Z)} = \frac{(d/d\lambda)[\epsilon_X C_X/\epsilon_Z]}{(d/d\lambda)(\epsilon_Y/\epsilon_Z)} + C_Y \quad (4)$$

If the first derivative of eq. (4) is taken since the derivative of a constant (C_Y) is zero, eq. (5) would be obtained :

$$\frac{dD}{d\lambda} = \frac{d}{d\lambda} \left[\frac{(d/d\lambda)[\epsilon_X C_X/\epsilon_Z]}{(d/d\lambda)(\epsilon_Y/\epsilon_Z)} \right] \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5) is the mathematical foundation of multicomponent analysis that permits the determination of concentration of each of the active compounds in the solution (X in this equation) without interference from the other compounds of the ternary system (Y and Z in these equations). As eq. (5) shows there is a linear relation between the amount of $dD/d\lambda$ and the concentration of X in the solution. A calibration curve could be constructed by plotting $dD/d\lambda$ against concentration of X in the standard solutions of X or in the standard ternary mixtures. For more sensitivity the amount of $dD/d\lambda$ corresponding to maximum or minimum wavelength should be measured.

Calibration graphs for Y and Z could be also constructed as described for X.

The divisors spectra calculated as the following steps :

(a) A standard solution of each analyte added to the unknown sample and recorded its spectrum in the wavelength range of 220 to 320 nm.

(b) The spectrum of unknown sample recorded in the wavelength range of 220 to 320 nm.

(c) The spectrum of divisor in the presence of matrix effect calculated by the subtract the spectrum of step "b" from step "a".

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of the three compounds, aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol overlapped closely in the region of 220–320 nm in Fig. 1. For this reason, the determination of the above compounds was not possible from direct measurements of absorbances in the zero-order spectra. In this research, successive ratio spectra derivative method based on the spectrophotometric data was developed for the simultaneous analysis of the ternary mixtures containing ASP, AA and PAR without prior separation.

Fig. 1. Pure absorption spectra of aspirin, ascorbic acid, paracetamol and a ternary mixture of components. The concentration of each component is $10.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ in B-R buffer at pH 4.0.

Optimization of the parameters :

In the following, the effect of some parameters including pH and working wavelengths on the accuracy and sensitivity of the proposed method has been studied.

Optimization of pH :

It has been shown that the maximum absorbance for

aspirin and paracetamol is significantly independent to the pH of solution within the pH range of 2.0 to 6.0 (Fig. 2A) while, the sensitivity of ascorbic acid at pH of 4.0 is maximum. Also, the maximum wavelengths for AA and PAR are close to each other in the range of 2.0 to 3.0 and 5.0 to 7.0 but at pH 4.0, overlapping spectra between AA and PAR decreased (Fig. 2B), therefore B-R buffer at pH 4.0 was selected for adjust the pH of solutions before recording the spectra.

Fig. 2. The effect of pH on the A_{\max} (A) and λ_{\max} (B) for the spectra of ASP, AA and PAR. Conditions : ASP, 20.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; AA, 20.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and PAR, 20.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$.

Selection of the working wavelengths :

In the application of this method, the final derivative of the successive ratio spectra of pure compound and its ternary mixture would be coincided in the spectral region corresponding to a maximum point or a minimum point of the wavelength as shown in Fig. 3. These coinciding points of the derivative of the ratio spectra can be selected as working wavelengths for the determinations of the subject compounds in the ternary mixture. The best working wavelengths selected at 296, 257 and 261 nm

Fig. 3. The coincident spectra of the final derivative of the successive ratio spectra of : (A) ternary mixture of 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ASP, 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ AA and 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PAR, $\epsilon_{AA}/\epsilon_{ASP}$ as divisor; (B) 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ pure PAR, $\epsilon_{AA}/\epsilon_{ASP}$ as divisor; (C) ternary mixture of 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ASP, 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ AA and 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PAR, $\epsilon_{ASP}/\epsilon_{PAR}$ as divisor; (D) 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of pure AA, $\epsilon_{ASP}/\epsilon_{PAR}$ as divisor; (E) ternary mixture of 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ASP, 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ AA and 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PAR, $\epsilon_{PAR}/\epsilon_{AA}$ as divisor and (F) 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of pure ASP, $\epsilon_{PAR}/\epsilon_{AA}$ as divisor.

for determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol respectively.

Preliminary study :

Determination of aspirin in the presence of ascorbic acid and paracetamol :

For showing the applicability of the proposed method in the determination of ASP in the presence of AA and PAR. The absorption spectra of the ternary mixtures containing ASP+AA+PAR (10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for each component) after standard addition of three components (10–60 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) were recorded in the range of 220–320 nm (Fig. 4) and divided by the spectrum of the standard solution of AA that was 20.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and the ratio spectra were obtained (Fig. 5). First derivatives of the ratio spectra were obtained with $\Delta\lambda = 1$ nm (Fig. 6). After that, these vectors (first derivatives of the ratio spectra) are divided by $(d/d\lambda)(\epsilon_{PAR}/\epsilon_{AA})$ corresponding to the derivative of the ratio of the spectra of PAR that was 20.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and AA that was 20.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ under the optimum conditions and therefore, second ratio spectra (according to eq. (4)) were obtained (Fig. 7). First derivative of these vectors were obtained with $\Delta\lambda = 1$ nm (Fig. 8). The concentration of aspirin was determined as 9.3 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ using standard addition plot by measuring the amplitude at 296 nm corresponding to a minimum wavelength shown in Fig. 8. Table 1 shows the divisors used in the successive ratio spectra derivative method for simulta-

Fig. 4. The spectra of the ternary mixture of ASP + AA + PAR after simultaneous standard additions of three components in the same mole ratios at the concentration range of 0–60 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for spectra 1–7. The initial solution contains a ternary mixture of ASP ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), AA ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and PAR ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) in B-R buffer at pH 4.0.

Fig. 5. Ratio spectra for a ternary mixture of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol after simultaneous standard additions of three components in the concentration range of 0–60 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (1 to 7). Divisor : ϵ_{AA} in B-R buffer at pH 4.0. The initial solution contains a ternary mixture of ASP ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), AA ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and PAR ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$).

Fig. 6. First derivative for the spectra in Fig. 4. $\Delta\lambda = 1.0 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 7. Ratio spectra for the first derivative spectra in Fig. 5. Divisor : $d(\epsilon_{AA})/d\lambda$ in B-R buffer at pH 4.0.

Fig. 8. First derivative for the spectra in Fig. 6. $\Delta\lambda = 1.0 \text{ nm}$.

Table 1. Successive ratio spectra derivative parameters for simultaneous determination of ASP, AA and PAR

Component	Steps	Divisors	Working wavelength (nm)
Aspirin	1	ϵ_{AA}	–
	2	$d(\epsilon_{PAR}/\epsilon_{AA})/d\lambda$	296
Ascorbic acid	1	ϵ_{PAR}	–
	2	$d(\epsilon_{ASP}/\epsilon_{PAR})/d\lambda$	257
Paracetamol	1	ϵ_{ASP}	–
	2	$d(\epsilon_{AA}/\epsilon_{ASP})/d\lambda$	261

neous determination of ASP, AA and PAR in the presence of each other with their corresponding working wavelengths.

Figures of merit :

To check the reproducibility of the proposed method, three replicate experiments for the determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol in ternary mixtures have been designed (Table 2). The relative standard deviation values are in the range of 1.08 to 5.79%.

Table 2. Reproducibility of the proposed method for simultaneous determination of ASP, AA and PAR in some ternary mixtures by the proposed method

Mixture	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			RSD (%)		
	ASP	AA	PAR	ASP	AA	PAR	ASP	AA	PAR
1	10	10	10	9.11	10.21	9.76			
2	10	10	10	9.58	10.96	9.23	5.79	4.62	2.07
3	10	10	10	10.38	10.04	9.38			
4	50	10	50	50.72	9.80	49.37			
5	50	10	50	51.30	10.20	50.48	3.29	2.05	1.18
6	50	10	50	48.20	9.91	49.83			
7	10	50	50	10.10	49.78	48.52			
8	10	50	50	10.65	50.34	51.50	5.23	1.08	3.28
9	10	50	50	9.59	50.87	48.86			

Table 3. Determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol in some ternary mixtures

Sr. no.	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Recovery (%)		
	ASP	AA	PAR	ASP	AA	PAR	ASP	AA	PAR
1	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.20	10.70	10.00	102.10	106.80	100.00
2	20.0	20.0	20.0	20.50	19.80	20.10	102.60	99.20	100.50
3	20.0	50.0	50.0	19.30	50.00	49.00	96.30	100.00	98.00
4	10.0	100.0	100.0	10.20	100.30	100.00	102.30	100.30	100.00
5	100.0	5.0	5.0	100.60	4.80	5.00	100.60	96.80	100.00
6	10.0	70.0	70.0	10.60	69.60	69.90	105.90	99.40	99.80
7	70.0	10.0	10.0	71.30	9.90	10.11	100.30	98.90	101.10
8	5.0	20.0	20.0	5.00	19.70	20.32	101.90	99.00	101.15
9	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.20	49.50	50.00	97.20	95.20	100.00
10	5.0	5.0	5.0	4.90	4.80	5.00	99.20	98.70	100.00

Table 4. Determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol in some pharmaceutical formulation by the proposed method

Sample	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Recovery (%)		
	ASP	AA	PAR	ASP	AA	PAR	ASP	AA	PAR
Afebryl	–	–	–	11.44	12.83	9.02	94.00	105.01	90.20
tablet	3.00	3.00	3.00	14.30	13.30	12.02	95.30	100.60	100.00
	5.00	5.00	5.00	16.73	14.98	13.96	105.80	94.00	98.80
Effervescent	–	–	–	4.29	72.32	–	102.14	98.66	–
powder	10.00	10.00	–	23.14	81.26	–	100.21	97.90	–
	20.00	20.00	–	23.78	91.23	–	98.26	98.23	–
Average							99.28	99.07	96.33
RSD (%)							4.42	3.66	5.55

The calibration plots were linear in the ranges of 0.4–320.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, 0.8–160.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and 0.8–160.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ respectively for PAR, ASP and AA with the $r > 0.99$.

The limit of detection calculated as $\text{LOD} = 3S_C^{15}$, where S_C is the standard deviation of several ($n = 3$)

replicated measurement of zero concentration of the analyte using the proposed method. The corresponding values obtained were 0.29, 0.76 and 0.48 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for ASP, AA and PAR, respectively.

Application of the proposed method :

In order to evaluate the applicability of the proposed

method for the determination of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol in the real samples, the utility of the developed method was tested by determining of the compounds in several model (mixed) samples (Table 2) and pharmaceutical formulations (Table 3). The good recoveries of the spiked samples are indicative of the successful applicability of the proposed method for simultaneous determination of ASP, AA and PAR in the presence of each other. All of the recoveries in real samples were satisfactory in the range of 94.0% to 105.8%.

Conclusion

This work formulates a new approach to the simultaneous analysis of ternary mixtures of aspirin, ascorbic acid and paracetamol which have overlapping spectra. In the successive ratio spectra derivative method, for each compound in ternary mixture, without searching for the critical point for the separated peaks, the maximum amplitude of the separated peaks can be measured. This can be considered as an advantage of the proposed method over alternative methods for the resolution of ternary mixtures. Also, standard addition can be easily used in the proposed method and matrix effects can be removed. Therefore, this method can be used for resolving ternary mixtures in the complex samples with unknown matrices. In multivariate methods such as PLS standard addition can be used but that needs another procedure known as generalized standard addition method¹⁶.

The proposed method has great promise for the routine analysis of two or more compounds in mixtures and for the analysis of Afebryl tablet and effervescent powders containing ascorbic acid and paracetamol in control process of products.

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References

1. J. Verdu-Andres, F. Bosch-Reig and P. Campins-Falco, *Analyst*, 1995, **120**, 299.
2. E. Dinc and F. Onur, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1998, **356**, 93.
3. S. Wold, M. Sjoström and L. Eriksson, *Chem. Intel. Lab. Syst.*, 2001, **58**, 109.
4. E. Dinc, C. Yucesoy and F. Onur, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002, **58**, 1091.
5. M. Blanco, J. Gene, H. Iturriaga, S. Maspoch and J. Riba, *Talanta*, 1987, **34**, 987.
6. F. Bosch-Reig and P. Campins-Falco, *Analyst*, 1988, **113**, 1011.
7. A. T Giese and C. S. French, *Appl. Spectros.*, 1955, **9**, 78.
8. T.-C. O'Haver and G.-L. Green, *Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **48**, 312.
9. T. C. O'Haver, *Anal. Chem.*, 1979, **51**, 91A.
10. R. Rohilla and U. Gupta, *E-J. Chem.*, 2012, **9**, 1357.
11. F. Salinas, J. J. Berzas Nevado and M. A. Espinosa, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 347.
12. J. J. Berzas Nevado, C. C. Guiberteau and F. Salinas, *Talanta*, 1992, **39**, 547.
13. E. Dinc, *Talanta*, 1999, **48**, 1145.
14. E. Dinc, E. Baydan, M. Kanbur and F. Onur, *Talanta*, 2002, **58**, 579.
15. J. C. Miller and J. N. Miller, "Statistics for Analytical Chemistry", 3rd ed., Ellis Horwood, New York, 1993.
16. D. L. Massart, B. G. M. Vandeginste, L. M. C. Buydens, S. D. E. Jong, P. J. Lewi and J. Smeyers-Verbeke, "Handbook of Chemometrics and Qualimetrics; Part A", Elsevier Science, 1997.

